

Reflecting on search histories: a survey design to uncover users' cognitive and motivational processes

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1. Introduction

Understanding users' cognitive and motivational processes during search is crucial for identifying information needs and informing user-centered system design. Most existing studies on search behavior rely on methods such as log analyses, experiments or surveys (Lewandowski, 2015; Lewandowski, 2018; Silverstein et al., 1999). Log studies offer large-scale behavioral insights but lack access to users' internal states (He & Yilmaz, 2017; Jansen, 2006). Controlled experiments provide detailed behavioral observations but are prone to bias due to artificial settings and observer effects (Kelly et al. 2015; Levitt & List, 2007; Liu et al., 2019; Strzelecki, 2020). Surveys can reveal motivational and behavioral patterns at scale but often suffer from recall bias and constrain responses through closed-ended questions (Artino et al., 2022; Ochoa & Revilla, 2023; Porta et al., 2014; Tourangeau et al., 2000). Although these approaches have uncovered valuable behavioral patterns, they fall short in capturing the cognitive and emotional processes underlying real-world, in-the-moment search activity. In contrast, qualitative methods such as interviews or diary studies offer deeper insights into these internal states but are typically limited in scale (Bolger et al., 2003; Olorunfemi, 2024; Wutich et al., 2024).

Building on calls to integrate methods to overcome limitations of individual approaches (Lewandowski, 2017), we present a novel study design that embeds qualitative reflection within a one-shot survey. Specifically, we ask participants to review their actual search history and respond to structured reflection prompts that uncover their search goals, behaviors, and expectations. While our focus is on web search sessions, the methodology generalizes to other systems with retrievable interaction histories. Our contribution lies in offering a scalable yet contextually rich lens into real-world search activity, bridging behavioral data with users' cognitive and emotional states.

2. Study design

We developed a structured, one-shot survey that combines diary-style reflections with actual user behavior by prompting participants ($N=86$) to review and reflect on their recent search histories. The survey was administered via Qualtrics, with participants recruited through Prolific. After providing informed consent, participants followed step-by-step instructions to access their search history (Google, Bing, Yahoo) to confirm eligibility. In practice, nearly all participants used Google, only one reported using Bing. The survey began with general questions about participants' typical search engine usage.

Next, participants were asked to review and reflect on their last three search sessions, which we defined in line with Jansen et al. (2008) as '*a series of interactions by the user to address a single information need*'. To guide their reflection, we developed open-ended questions based on Xie's (2002) multi-level search goal framework, covering current, leading, long-term goals, and interactive intention. We extended the framework by adding an outcome realization dimension to capture how participants ultimately used the retrieved information. Additionally, participants rated satisfaction and typicality of each session.

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To contextualize responses, we assessed participants' attitudes towards artificial intelligence (Sindermann et al., 2021) and search engines (Urman et al., 2024), digital literacy (Hargittai & Hsieh, 2012) and demographics.

3. Design benefits

Our study design offers several advantages for capturing users' cognitive and motivational processes during search. First, anchoring reflections in participants' actual search history and focusing on their three most recent sessions reduces recall and selection bias, better capturing everyday search behavior (Bolger et al., 2003; Tourangeau et al., 2000; Tversky & Kahneman, 1974). Moreover, the structured, multi-level prompts encourage participants to articulate deeper motivations and outcomes, moving beyond surface-level responses. At the same time, the approach remains scalable: from 86 participants, we collected 247 session-level reflections, showing that rich insights can be obtained without sacrificing breadth. Finally, the method is transferable to other domains such as generative AI-based chatbot use and adaptable for large-scale studies using narrower prompts or data donation approaches that allow for a more streamlined reflection process.

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